

D2.1 Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Engagement Plan

30/09/2025

Abstract

This document outlines strategic approaches for effective project communication, innovation management, including IP management of exploitable assets, and stakeholder engagement, including user community involvement and training.

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Work Package 2			
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Executive Summary

The Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation And Engagement Plan deliverable outlines the strategic framework for maximising the impact and ensuring the long-term sustainability of the EOSC Data Commons project. As a key contribution to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), the project's overarching goal is to establish a trusted European Research Commons where researchers can easily find, access, analyze, and reuse high-quality, interoperable research data. This plan details the integrated processes, tools, and responsibilities implemented in WP2 of the project and that will govern the project's innovation management, intellectual property (IP) strategy, communication, dissemination and user engagement activities throughout its lifecycle. It is structured in 3 main activities:

Innovation and Exploitation Management (Task 2.1) establishes a rigorous Innovation Management System (IMS) to systematically monitor and manage all exploitable assets. Including Background, Results, Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and innovations are tracked in a dedicated Register of Exploitable Assets, documenting their maturity level (TRL), ownership, Intellectual Property Rights, Access conditions, exploitation paths, sustainability plans and expected impact. Baseline strategy is guided by the principle: "As open as possible, as closed as necessary". All software developed or improved will be licensed under permissive Open Source licenses to facilitate widespread adoption and reuse by the scientific community and industry. Non-software outputs, such as documentation and guidelines, will be made available under Creative Commons (CC BY 4.0) licenses. This approach ensures transparency while maximising the project's impact on the Open Science ecosystem. Initial KERs are provided together with baseline information:

- KER1: AI-based Analytics Oriented Metadata Warehouse and Discovery Service (EOSC Matchmaker).
- KER2: Federation of Data Repositories.
- KER3: Catalogue of Analytics for Research Communities.
- KER4: EOSC Data Commons Execution Service (EOSC Data Player).
- KER5: Harmonised metadata specification for processing datasets.
- KER6: FAIRness assessment and reproducibility toolset and policies to assist Data FAIRness.

Communication, Dissemination, and Service Promotion (Task 2.2) focuses on raising the visibility of the project and promoting its services, particularly the two main operational tools, the EOSC Matchmaker and the EOSC Data Player. The strategy relies on maintaining a central project website, utilising social media, and distributing an external newsletter. Critically, all public deliverables, training materials, and scientific publications will be deposited and made Open Access via the EOSC Data Commons Community on Zenodo.

Stakeholder and User Community Engagement (Task 2.3): Engagement is prioritised to ensure the project remains responsive to real-world needs. Activities include conducting an initial survey to assess the technical readiness and needs of participating repositories and data providers. Subsequent focus groups and targeted training activities will be coordinated

to strengthen the capacity of user communities and ensure the successful uptake of project results beyond the consortium.

1. Introduction

Researchers face challenges when managing and sharing vast amounts of data. As explained in the DoA, many struggle with accessing high-quality, interoperable research outputs. This situation can lead to slower progress and less impactful discoveries. Without a unified system, the potential of valuable research data often goes untapped. In this context, the EU-funded EOSC Data Commons project will contribute to establishing the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) as the European Research Commons. This framework is expected to provide a trusted ecosystem where researchers can easily access, share, and use research data. The project will improve data management, making finding, analysing, and reusing research outputs easier. By working with a wide range of partners, EOSC Data Commons seeks to empower researchers across various fields in Europe.

1.1. Scope and Purpose of the document

This document aims to report the Communications, Dissemination, Exploitation and Engagement Plan for the project. It includes the description of the processes, responsibilities, and tools that will be applied to ensure that project results are effectively captured, protected, disseminated, and exploited for maximum impact. Its scope covers the full lifecycle of innovation management within the project, from the identification and refinement of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) to their uptake, adoption, and long-term sustainability. The plan establishes clear procedures for the management of intellectual property rights (IPR), ensuring that all project assets are handled appropriately and that partners are equipped to exploit results both individually and collectively. It also sets out strategies for communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement, including the organisation of flagship events, participation in third-party events, and proactive liaison with research, industry, and public sector actors. Finally, the plan defines measures to strengthen the capacity of user communities through targeted training activities, ensuring that knowledge transfer is effective and that project results achieve broad adoption beyond the consortium.

1.2. Structure of the document

The document is structured following way:

- The first chapter provides the general introduction.
- Second chapter describes the Innovation Management System defined for the project including the main activities and tasks the IP management, exploitation and sustainability plans the contractual baseline and the next steps

- The third chapter provides the Dissemination and Communications plan. It includes the initial communication tools available for the project, branding material, templates, project website, use of social media newsletters and events.
- Forth chapter describes the plan for stakeholder and user community engagement, and the training and feedback expected to be collected
- Fifth chapter is the general conclusion and next steps
- Templates and other relevant information linked to the three main tasks are provided in the annexes.

1.3. Context

The Communications, Dissemination, Exploitation and Engagement Plan is developed within the framework of Work Package 2 (Innovation, Exploitation, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement), which provides the foundation for ensuring that project results achieve visibility, uptake, and long-term impact. WP2 is structured into three complementary tasks, each addressing a critical dimension of innovation management and collectively forming an integrated strategy.

- Task 2.1. Innovation Management, IP Management, Exploitation and Sustainability. establishes the core Innovation Management System of the project. This system provides the processes and procedures for capturing, curating, and assessing project results across the innovation lifecycle
- Task 2.2. Communication, Dissemination and Service Promotion complements this by ensuring that the project’s results and activities are effectively communicated to diverse audiences
- Task 2.3. Stakeholder and User Community Engagement, Training and Feedback ensures that the project is responsive to the needs and expectations of its key stakeholders, including user research communities, repository owners, and related Research Infrastructure (RI) and EOSC projects.

Figure 1: Innovation, Exploitation, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Global Overview

The main work package outputs are:

- D2.1 Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Engagement Plan (M6)
- D2.2 Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Engagement Progress Report (M18)
- D2.3 Policy brief reporting period no.1 (M18)
- D2.4 Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Engagement Final Report (M36)
- D2.5 Policy brief reporting period no.2 (M36)

In order to build and collect the different results and generate all the necessary news and dissemination activities a thorough review of all the other deliverables will be done including D1.2 the Data Management Plans to understand the Data outputs of the project, and the deliverables from the technical work packages (WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6) will provide the necessary information to understand the technology components and services developed during the project.

The frame of the work related to this work package is bound to the following legal documents:

- Grant Agreement No. 101188179 between the European Commission and the Coordinator
- Consortium Agreement between all project partners

Those specific articles and clauses regulate Exploitation, Results, Ownership and joint ownership, Access, and Open Science among others. The relevant definitions for some of those have been included in the next sections for further clarity of the document.

1.4. Definitions

- **Objectives:** *“The goals of the work performed within the project, in terms of its research and innovation content. This will be translated into the project’s activities. These may range from tackling specific research questions, demonstrating the feasibility of innovation, sharing knowledge among stakeholders on specific issues. The nature of the objectives will depend on the type of action, and the scope of the topic.”* (Reference: [European Commission Horizon Europe Guidelines](#))
- **Outcomes:** *“The expected effects, over the medium term, of projects supported under a given topic. The results of a project should contribute to these outcomes, fostered in particular by the dissemination and exploitation measures (including the uptake, diffusion, deployment, and/or use of the project’s results by direct target groups). Outcomes generally occur during or shortly after the end of the project”* (Reference: [European Commission Horizon Europe Guidelines](#))
- **Impacts:** *“Wider long term effects on society (including the environment), the economy and science, enabled by the outcomes of R&I investments (long term). It refers to the*

specific contribution of the project to the work programme expected impacts described in the destination. Impacts generally occur some time after the end of the project” (Reference: [European Commission Horizon Europe Guidelines](#))

- **Dissemination:** *“The public disclosure of the results by appropriate means, other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results, including by scientific [or professional] publications in any medium.”* (Reference: [Grant Agreement Annex 5](#))
- **Exploit(ation):** *“The use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including among other things, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities”*(Reference: [Grant Agreement Annex 5](#)).
- **Innovation:** *“The successful exploitation of new creations (inventions) which can be used to produce tangible benefit, satisfying needs and wants.* (Reference: [IP Helpdesk Webinars](#))
- **Background:** *means any data, know-how or information – whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights – that is: (a) held by the beneficiaries before they acceded to the Agreement and (b) needed to implement the action or exploit the results* (Reference: [Grant Agreement Annex 5](#))
- **Results:** *“Means any tangible or intangible effect of the action, such as data, know-how or information, whatever its form or nature, whether or not it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights.”* (Reference: [Grant Agreement Annex 5](#)). *What is generated during the project implementation. This may include, for example, know-how, innovative solutions, algorithms, proof of feasibility, new business models, policy recommendations, guidelines, prototypes, demonstrators, databases and datasets, trained researchers, new infrastructures, networks, etc. Most project results (inventions, scientific works, etc) are ‘Intellectual Property’, which may, if appropriate, be protected by formal ‘Intellectual Property Rights* (Reference: [European Commission Horizon Europe Guidelines](#))
- **Key Exploitable Result:** *A Key Exploitable Result (KER) is an identified main interesting result (as defined above) which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be “exploited” – meaning to make use and derive benefits- downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education.* (Reference: [European Commission Horizon Europe Guidelines](#))
- **Intellectual Property (IP):** *“Refers to creations/products of the mind, such as inventions, research & experimentation or products of creativity. Like physical property, IP is an asset which can be traded (sold, bought, leased, used or given away), and is protected by law.”* (Reference: [IP Helpdesk Glossary](#))
- **Intellectual Property Rights (IPR):** *Is the legal right granted to IP owners to protect their IP, enabling people to earn recognition or financial benefit from what they invent or create. Some common types of IPR are: (i) Copyright (Software, written works, engineering drawings...) – it comes into existence automatically upon the creation of the original work, (ii) Patents (Technical inventions) - a monopoly right granted in return for causing the publication of an invention, preventing others to use it without agreement, (iii) Database rights (Creation & arrangement of data) - legal rights that protect the creation & management of data), (iv) Design rights (Appearance), (v)*

Trademarks, (vi) Confidentiality Agreements (Know-how). (Reference: [IP Helpdesk Glossary](#))

- **Ownership & Joint Ownership of Results:** *“Results are owned by the beneficiaries that generate them. However, two or more beneficiaries own results jointly if: - they have jointly generated them and it is not possible to: (i) establish the respective contribution of each beneficiary, or (ii) separate them for the purpose of applying for, obtaining or maintaining their protection. The joint owners must agree – in writing – on the allocation and terms of the exercise of their joint ownership (‘joint ownership agreement’), to ensure compliance with their obligations under this Agreement.”* (Reference: [Grant Agreement Annex 5](#))
- **Access Rights** - *“Rights to use results or background”.* (Reference: [Grant Agreement Annex 5](#))
- **Fair and reasonable conditions:** *“Appropriate conditions, including possible financial terms or royalty-free conditions, taking into account the specific circumstances of the request for access, for example the actual or potential value of the results or background to which access is requested and/or the scope, duration or other characteristics of the exploitation envisaged.”* (Reference: [Grant Agreement Annex 5](#))
- **Research outputs** – *“Results to which access can be given in the form of scientific publications, data or other engineered results and processes such as software, algorithms, protocols, models, workflows and electronic notebooks.”* (Reference: [Grant Agreement Annex 5](#))
- **Open access:** *“Online access to research outputs provided free of charge to the end-user.”* (Reference: [Grant Agreement Annex 5](#))
- **Open science:** *“An approach to the scientific process based on open cooperative work, tools and diffusing knowledge.* (Reference: [Grant Agreement Annex 5](#))
- **FAIR principles** – *‘findability’, ‘accessibility’, ‘interoperability’ and ‘reusability’.* (Reference: [Grant Agreement Annex 5](#))
- **Technology Readiness Levels - TRL Levels** (Reference: [Annex G Horizon 2020 Grant Agreement](#))
 - TRL 1 – basic principles observed
 - TRL 2 – technology concept formulated
 - TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept
 - TRL 4 – technology validated in the lab
 - TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
 - TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
 - TRL 7 system prototype demonstration in an operational environment
 - TRL 8 – system complete and qualified
 - TRL 9 – actual system is proven in an operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space)

2. Innovation and Exploitation Management

2.1. Introduction

The Exploitation and Sustainability Management approach within EOSC Data Commons project is developed from the Innovation Management know-how developed within the EGI Foundation along many projects (EOSC-hub¹, C-Scale², iImagine³, interTwin⁴, SPECTRUM⁵, ANERIS⁶, etc.) and adapts some of the guidelines provided by ISO 56002:2019 Innovation management – Innovation management system into a Horizon Europe Project.

Main activities foreseen in the Innovation Management System are:

- Results Collection and IP Management
- Exploitation Management and Sustainability Planning
- Impact assessment

Exploitation activities will be managed in T2.1 by the Innovation Manager. Project results will be regularly monitored and necessary information on ownership, IP protection and access will be collected to comply with the Results Ownership List (ROL) and the IPR Continuous Reporting. Relevant information related to KERs will be collected and aligned with the Horizon Results Platform (HRP), see Annex 1. It will include service/product descriptions and metadata and the opportunities to maximise project impact. To support the evolution of the KERs, a Champion is assigned to each KER to liaise with the involved partners, monitor progress and assist in realising the exploitation strategy.

2.2. Work Plan

All three activities will be executed by the Innovation Manager during the whole duration of the project that will need to be regularly updated for the necessary milestones, deliverables and communications activities. In order to manage those, a procedure for innovation management has been described within D1.1 and is being followed. During the first months following activities have been implemented:

Table 1: T2.1 Workplan

Activity #	Setting up the Innovation Management System	Timeline
1	Creates/Updates a specific space in the repository (confluence) to collect Innovation Management Plan and all necessary templates for the register of exploitable assets,	March - April 2025

¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/777536>

² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101017529>

³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058625>

⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058386>

⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101131550>

⁶ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101094924>

D2.1 Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Engagement Plan

Activity #	Setting up the Innovation Management System	Timeline
	Key exploitable results catalogue and all the necessary information linked to those.	
2	Desk research and careful analysis of project official documentation DoA, project proposal and CA to create the baseline information for the definition of the Innovation Management Plan, initial entries for Key Exploitable Results and expected results	May-June 2025
3	WP2 members iterate and validates information	March-Sept 2025
4	Based on the desk research KER Champion/Result Contact Person linked to each of the KERs/Project Results are identified and appointed. New contact persons can be appointed or changed anytime in the project in case it is needed.	June 2025
5	The resulting Innovation Management Plan including baseline information for Key Exploitable Results and Expected Results is validated by IEG, AMB and/or PMO. The output is published in the corresponding deliverable (D2.1)	June-Sept 2025

For the actual implementation of the plan following activities are foreseen. Timeline shows the timings till the next milestone.

Activity #	Regular update of the Innovation Management Information	Timeline
1	Desk research and careful analysis of deliverables, milestones, DoA, project proposal, presentations and other dissemination material generated by the project.	Sept - December 2025
2	KER Champions/Results Owners validate and consolidate of information related to relevant exploitable assets / KERs -including IPR, Access Rights and dissemination and exploitation plans in line with the policies of the owning organisations	December 2025
3	Periodically, WP2 members iterate and validates information	Sept- March 2026
4	Periodically, IEG, AMB, PMO and/or GA review the progress of Innovation Management activities against the plan, suggest and validate any update in the repository entries	Sept- March 2026
5	Publishes updated & validated innovation management progress information into the relevant WP2 deliverables (D2.x), Progress Reports, Review Presentations and for Dissemination and Communications activities (such as web content, news, publications, etc)	March 2026

Procedure will be iterated for the subsequent deliverables switching the focus to the specific needs of each of them.

2.3. Results Collection and IP Management

2.3.1. Identification of exploitable assets

To ensure systematic monitoring, management, and valorisation of project outputs, a Register of Exploitable Assets will be established and maintained throughout the project. Exploitable assets are those elements of the project that can be used and exploited after the end of the project. This register will serve as a living knowledge base, capturing relevant information on partner backgrounds, results, innovations, and Key Exploitable Results (KERs). Its purpose is to provide transparency on ownership, access conditions, and exploitation opportunities, thereby facilitating effective uptake and sustainability of project results.

- **Background** is initially collected as an annex of the consortium agreement and will be maintained throughout the project by updating it within the project internal register. Each partner will specify access rights for implementation and for potential exploitation.
- **Results per partner:** For each result generated, a short description will be provided, including target users/groups, the current and achieved maturity level (Technology Readiness Level, TRL), details of the work carried out in the project, and supporting documentation or references (e.g., deliverables, publications, demonstrators, datasets, software repositories).
- **Key Exploitable Results (KERs):** The register will capture extended descriptions of each KER in line with Horizon Europe Horizon platform. Information will include the background needed, sub-components, and identified exploitation paths. This information will be refined iteratively in collaboration with KER Champions, the appointed project representatives of the WP or Task where the KERs are generated and who will support with the overall understanding.
- **Innovations:** For those results and Key Exploitable Results successfully adopted or with highest exploitation potential, the register will further document their value proposition, innovative aspects, positioning within the competitive landscape.

The baseline for the KERs as explained in the Description of Action of the project are:

- **KER1:** AI-based Analytics Oriented Metadata Warehouse and Discovery Service (AI-MWDS rebranded to EOSC Matchmaker). Service for AI-based discovery of pairs of data and related analytics tools over a Metadata Warehouse (output WP4 & WP5). Project Results: Index Search, Vector Database, Virtual Knowledge Graph.
- **KER2:** Federation of Data Repositories. Set of national, institutional and thematic data repositories that feed the Metadata Warehouse (output WP3 & WP4). Project Results: Sector-specific metadata crawlers, Technology-specific metadata crawlers.

- KER3: Catalogue of Analytics for Research Communities. Catalogue of services, software, workflows and tools from research communities. It aggregates and extends existing registries, allowing a single point of discovery for analytics applicable to processing data from the Federation of Data Repositories (output WP5). Project Results: Connectors towards tool registries.
- KER4: EOSC Data Commons Execution Service (DAODS rebranded to EOSC Data Player). Pluggable modular service to deploy and execute the data analysis using the metadata descriptions on the required compute infrastructure (output WP6). Project Results: Dispatcher, Plugins for compute engines, Data Access Layer.
- KER5: Harmonised metadata specification for processing datasets. Harmonised metadata specification for encoding a request for processing one or more datasets, using one or more tools, and accommodating a variety of deployment and processing platforms (output WP5). Project Results: Specification of the package for processing datasets.
- KER6: FAIRness assessment and reproducibility toolset and policies to assist Data FAIRness. Integration of the toolset to increase the FAIRness of Data and enable reproducibility of science together with the set of policies and recommendations to assist researchers for data curation and FAIRness (output WP4). Project Results: FAIRness assessment and reproducibility toolset, Policies to assist Data FAIRness.

2.3.2. IP Management

The EOSC Data Commons global IP strategy aims to maximise uptake and minimise barriers to adoption, adaptation, and reuse following the Open Science approach to be as open as possible, as closed as necessary as explained in the DoA. Most of the exploitable results are expected to be software (SW) and workflows shared under Free and Open Source Software licenses, and associated support documentation, service definitions and associated know-how and recommendations that will be documented and shared under Open Science compliant Creative Commons copyright. Special arrangements will be done to ensure confidentiality and protection of personal data whenever it is needed.

- The know-how generated will be mainly shared by documenting and performing dissemination and training activities. As such presentations, documents, data, frameworks, publications, and guidelines will be available under Creative Commons licenses (CC BY 4.0) unless a legitimate interest from the owner prevents them from doing it. There are no patents foreseen; in case an opportunity arises, the partner or group of partners generating the IP to protect will cover the costs and will inform the Innovation Manager ensuring shortest embargo time as possible.
- For software, integration into RIs and EOSC Nodes may require seamless incorporation of IP from various sources. The project will provide support and specifications to manage this multi-party IP efficiently. SW code developed or improved by the project will be licensed under permissive Open Source licenses whenever possible. Improvements to existing software will be assigned to the owners of the background IP and will adopt the same permissive license. Copyright in the source code will not be asserted for research or commercial use, providing flexibility for commercial applications. Specific training for IP management and SW licensing is expected to be delivered for partners during the project. The JLA

compatibility checker⁷ will be used when SW has components from different sources to check that inbound and outbound licensing terms are compatible. The project's open science approach will likely cover all knowledge and data captured, with consideration of sui generis database⁸ rights for eligible collections.

Intellectual Property Management:

During the project, a Result Ownership List will be collected and maintained, in line with the provisions for Horizon Europe's Continuous Reporting, to ensure clear ownership and facilitate exploitation of project results. It will document the responsible partner(s), the associated intellectual property rights (IPR), and the access status for internal and external use. For those results developed jointly by multiple partners, formal Joint Ownership Agreements (JoAs) will be established to define rights, responsibilities, and conditions for use and exploitation.

Figure 2: Results Collection and IP Management

2.4. Exploitation Management and Sustainability Planning

Following GA definition of exploitation following paths are considered which can be for Non-Commercial (academic, policy, etc.) or Commercial purposes:

- **Further Research:** Refers to academic or industrial research conducted within the project that is aligned with the partners' long-term research goals. It is often focused on technologies in the early stages of development (low TRL) aiming to increase the maturity, those intended for educational purposes, or those that need new features and adaptations. Specific research groups or departments within the partners' organisations are usually responsible for further developing and utilising the project results internally.
- **Product:** This is a straightforward path for fostering the project uptake. There can be different types of products ranging from research oriented products aiming to

⁷ <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/eupl/solution/joinup-licensing-assistant/jla-compatibility-checker>

⁸ <https://www.openaire.eu/sui-generis-database-right-sgdr>

facilitate further research, to commercial ready products. Spanning project results to ready-to-use / ready-for-sale solutions entails allocating efforts in documentation, protection, certification, alignment with standards, and marketing, among others. Creating a well-defined product can also facilitate their exploitation via technology transfer or licensing between project partners or external parties.

- Services: Refers to the creation of services related to the technologies and knowledge generated in the project, such as software as a service, consulting services, or support services. These services can be offered through service-level agreements or linked to other types of contracts, such as licensing, collaboration, or consortium agreements.
- Standardisation: This exploitation path can be crucial for the adoption of project generated knowledge. Standardisation activities can involve contributing to the standardisation body, which can adopt part of the project-generated knowledge for the creation or the improvement of standards. Another way is to ensure the alignment of the technologies with existing standards so they can interoperate and facilitate their uptake.

Initial plan for exploitation, as presented in the DoA includes:

- EDC exploitation through services: Two main operational services that will be developed and made available to the research community: (1) AI-based Analytics-Oriented Metadata Warehouse and Discovery Service (EOSC Matchmaker) (KER1) and (2) EOSC Data Commons Execution service for the Data Analysis Orchestration and Deployment (EOSC Data Player) (KER4). During the project the necessary preconditions and policies will be defined so they can be onboarded as an EGI/EOSC service in the future.
- Exploitation through Products: All services encompass many software components and sub-services that will be developed, enhanced, adapted or re-used during the project and that can be exploited as stand-alone. They will be made available from open repositories (such as GitHub or specific landing pages), which will be available from EOSC Data Commons website and shared under an open-source license and with the necessary documentation in line with the quality and maturity levels to facilitate the use and re-use, and supported by the project partners owning the different components. Sustainability potential will be assessed for each of them. The project will ensure the exploitability of data products along the whole data lifecycle. Discovery service (KER1) together with the Federation of Data Repositories (KER2) will make the research data available. FAIRness assessment toolset (KER6) will be available to produce FAIR-by-design data, and further products and services will be available as part of the Catalogue of Tools (KER3) to be used or re-used.
- Standardisation and policy recommendation: The project also aims to standardise the way data catalogues, tools, and computing platforms and services interoperate. The Harmonised metadata specification for processing datasets (KER5) will ensure the interoperability between all the necessary data standards and the correct alignment with the needs of RIs and the EOSC IF. Any new specification will be proposed to be registered to the EOSC IF as interoperability guidelines and/or RI

policies. Specifically, the policies developed as part of the FAIRness Assessment (KER6) can be adopted by research communities.

- **Further Research:** The exploitation potential of the project is enormous as an enabler for **further research**. The project will establish a plan for collaboration with all EOSC-related projects (see Annex 1), enabling the use, reuse and further development of the results, and acting as a channel for future service adoption and growth. EOSC Data Commons will aid many future projects by enabling research communities to perform better science in all steps from data discovery, analysis, and long-term preservation, to reusability and replicability.

Sustainability Planning:

Towards the second half of the project the focus will be shifted to ensuring the economic sustainability of the project results and Key Exploitable results. The sustainability plan will address four key dimensions: ownership, access conditions, provision of maintenance and support, related costs, and expected return. Initial provisions for the sustainability plan includes the following provisions:

- All necessary agreements will be established and formalised, including joint ownership or licensing arrangements for software components, exploitation agreements for Key Exploitable Results (KERs), and operational/service level agreements (OLA/SLA) for services.
- The project website and social media will continue to be hosted by EGI, while all deliverables, including documentation, training materials, and user support resources, will remain accessible on Zenodo.
- Software developed within the project will be open source and shared via platforms such as GitHub, enabling ongoing access, adoption, and adaptation by users and contributors.
- Services will be adopted by EGI for the EGI Federation, with integration promoted across EOSC Nodes and Research Infrastructures, and updates and support provided by the designated result and service owners. Maintenance will be provided by the partners in charge of provisioning the service components.
- The Horizon Results Platform will be leveraged to enhance visibility and exploitation potential.
- Business Modelling Workshops conducted during the project will inform a sustainability strategy to ensure that services remain fully operational and continue delivering value beyond the project's lifespan.

Per Result and per partners

Figure 3: Exploitation Management and Sustainability Planning

Exploitation Baseline as indicated in the DoA:

Table 2: KER1-6 Exploitation Baseline

KER1: AI-based Analytics Oriented Metadata Warehouse and Discovery Service (EOSC Matchmaker)
<p>Expected exploitation paths:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adopted as EGI service and maintained by an open source community spawning from the project. • Adoption in RIs and NRENs (such as SWITCH and CESNET) - part of the research data lifecycle and its processing pipelines. • Aim to become an EOSC EU Node service and to be part of the EOSC Exchange of future EOSC Nodes (e.g. thematic, national, etc). • Discovery service is open and free to use via an accessible front-end. • Output of the discovery service used as input for the EOSC Data Commons Execution Service or any other interoperable service. <p>Components/Building Blocks: Analytics oriented Metadata Warehouse, AI-based Discovery, Tools for Data FAIRness Assessment and interfaces towards the Data Preparation component and the federated EOSC Resource Catalogue in the EOSC EU Node (OAI-PMH-interface). Data Preparation is composed of the Catalogue of tools, Packaging Hub for pairing data and software, and Request Packager for the dataset processing.</p> <p>Background/Sideground: SWITCH: harvesting pipelines, common metadata graphs, indexes and vector databases; SIB: virtualised graphs and research applications using LLMs; KNAW: metadata harvesting and harmonisation, application of AI for purposes of metadata enhancement, and development of novel approaches to search and discovery improvements and visualisation, and FAIR assessment best practices and applications.</p> <p>Ownership: EGI Foundation will own the service. Subcomponents owned by the partners who generated them.</p>

KER1: AI-based Analytics Oriented Metadata Warehouse and Discovery Service (EOSC Matchmaker)

IPR/Access rights: All related SW is distributed under a permissive Open Source license. Open Access to metadata warehouse and discovery service. Generated metadata under CC0 license.

KER2 - Federation of Data Repositories

Expected exploitation paths:

- Federated Data Repositories accessible by the discovery and execution services.
- New Data Repositories to be incorporated to the Federation to offer access to more data and capabilities.

Components/Building Blocks: Sector-specific metadata crawlers, Technology-specific metadata crawlers.

Background/Sideground: Repository Owners: different technologies empowering the repositories; COAR: extensive experience in developing good practices for repositories and engaging with the repository community to advocate and support their adoption. Active for many years in RDA, COAR is keenly aware of all trends, practices and requirements for repositories including FAIR principles.

Ownership: Consortium. Federated repositories are owned by the partner or 3rd party that generated them.

IPR/Access rights: Open Access documentation distributed under CC BY 4.0.

KER3: Catalogue of Analytics for Research Communities

Expected exploitation paths:

- Catalogue is open and free to use via an accessible front-end.
- Establishment of links between analytics tools and datasets metadata (part of KER1)

Components/Building Blocks: Connectors towards tool registries.

Background/Sideground: KNAW: prototyping experience with the construction of aggregated tools registries, and with challenges related to matching datasets and tools based on MIME Types.

Ownership: Consortium. Catalogue entries are owned by the partner or 3rd party that generated them

IPR/Access rights: Free and open access to the catalogue. Access to each catalogue entry under Fair and Reasonable conditions set by its owners.

KER4: Data Commons Execution Service (EOSC Data Player)

Expected exploitation paths:

- Adopted as EGI Service and maintained by an open source community spawning from the project
- Integration of the EOSC EU Node as the main deployment platform for the analytics tools and platforms.

KER4: Data Commons Execution Service (EOSC Data Player)

- Incorporate computing and storage resources from Research/National/Institutional Infrastructures, EGI or other EOSC Nodes for the deployment and execution of analytics tools and platforms.
- Aim to become an EOSC EU Node service and to be part of the EOSC Exchange of future EOSC Nodes (thematic, national).
- Integration of industrial & SME capabilities via EOSC and EGI DIH.

Components/Building Blocks: Dispatcher; Engine Plugins for deployment tools (Infrastructure Manager, Oscar and PaaS Orchestrator), computing services (Galaxy, JupyterHub, PlatformRRP), data access (OneData, ScienceMesh, FTS) and Compute Continuum (OpenStack, interLink, Kubernetes).

Background/Sideground: EGI: extensions for Jupyter Notebooks, Freiburg University: UseGalaxy.eu, ETH: RRP, UPV: IM, OSCAR, INFN: PaaS Orchestrator, interLink, UST/AGH: OneData, CERN ScienceMesh, FTS. 3rd party (OpenStack, Kubernetes, etc).

Ownership: EGI Foundation will own the service. Subcomponents owned by partners having generated them.

IPR/Access rights: All related SW is distributed under a permissive Open Source license. Access to execution services following AUP/Terms of Use and under OLA/SLA.

KER5 - Harmonised metadata specification for processing datasets

Expected exploitation paths:

- To be incorporated into the EOSC Interoperability Framework.
- Useful as a federating bridge between EOSC Nodes, and specifically for using the services in the EOSC EU node as a target infrastructure for executing the analysis.
- Also interesting for the interoperability within Data Spaces.

Components/Building Blocks: Specification of the package for processing datasets.

Background/Sideground: KNAW: packaging code and data for container-based deployment, and wide experience in deposit and export workflows based on the BagIt standard. Contribution to FAIR-IMPACT to disseminate and improve adoption of RO-Crate and Signposting. UPV: TOSCA definition for complex application architectures, to be extended with metadata for processing datasets.

Ownership: Consortium.

IPR/Access rights: Open Access specification distributed under CC BY 4.0.

KER6: FAIRness assessment and reproducibility toolset and policies to assist Data FAIRness

Expected exploitation paths:

- FAIRness awareness and assessment tools available as part of the Metadata Warehouse.
- Integration of best practices developed elsewhere (e.g. FAIR-IMPACT) into publication workflows.
- Integration available for re-use from an open repository.

KER6: FAIRness assessment and reproducibility toolset and policies to assist Data FAIRness

- Adoption of the toolset by the federated repositories and other repository owners (e.g. PANGAEA)

Components/Building Blocks: Pluggable, harmonised FAIR assessment Infrastructure & Tools from RIs, EOSC projects (e.g. OStrails) and other initiatives.

Background/Sideground: KNAW: development of FAIR best practices, compliance assessment software, and specific FAIR tools such as F-UJI and FAIR-Aware.

Ownership: KNAW. Subcomponents & Tools are owned by the partner or 3rd party that generated them.

IPR/Access rights: SW distributed under permissive open source license.

2.5. Impact Assessment (Scientific, Economic & Impact)

Within the DoA, the following pathways to impact are defined: (1) An optimised research data lifecycle, (2) Data FAIRness by design, (3) Pathway to interoperability and multidisciplinary cooperation, (4) Innovation through co-design and (5) Technology valorisation, sustainability and long-term availability. For each of those several indicators have been identified in order to monitor how they contribute to the outcomes during the project

Table 3: Outcome indicators

Pathway #1: An optimised research data lifecycle Outcome indicators	
#Services available	2
# Federated repositories*	20
# Execution engines supported*	6
# Data Management Engine supported*	3
# AI-powered data queries*	100 curated queries and >3000 automatically generated queries based on the curated ones) per month,
# Available tools in the catalogue*	2000+
# Analytics tools linked to datasets*	12

Pathway #2: Data FAIRness by design	Outcome indicators
# Tools and services for FAIRness assessment integrated*	3
# FAIRness evaluations performed	200
# Datasets with improved FAIRness*	100
# Research communities adopting the Data FAIRness toolset	10
# Policies for FAIR data*	2

Pathway #3: Pathway to interoperability and multidisciplinary cooperation	
# Supported domain-specific metadata schemas*	10
# Supported Technologies for Repositories	3
#Other Technologies Supported	10
# EOSC IF Interoperability Guideline for the package for processing datasets*	1

Pathway #4: Innovation through co-design	
# Use Cases*	13
# Scientific Domains	7

Pathway #5: Technology valorisation, sustainability and long-term availability	
#Exploitation-related agreements	3
#Integration with EOSC Nodes	2
# National repositories with datasets that can be analysed in EOSC EU Node via EOSC Data Commons	8
# Use cases that execute data analysis with EOSC EU Node services*	6

On a longer term (5-10 years) the project is expected to impact the following ways:

Impact 1: More innovation and higher productivity of research are enabled; new discoveries, breakthroughs, and innovations are facilitated: The project will enhance research efficiency and innovation capacity by providing advanced tools, services, and infrastructure that accelerate the generation of new knowledge. Scientific impact is achieved through faster discovery cycles, improved research reproducibility, and the facilitation of novel approaches across disciplines. Economic impact arises from the potential translation of research results into innovative products, technologies, and services, fostering competitiveness and creating opportunities for start-ups and SMEs. Societal impact is realised by enabling solutions to address pressing societal challenges, from healthcare and environmental monitoring to digital transformation, ultimately improving quality of life and public well-being.

Impact 2: More collaboration across scientific disciplines; increased sharing and reuse of data; systematic barriers hindering data and service sharing removed: By promoting cross-disciplinary collaboration and removing institutional, technical, and legal barriers to data and service sharing, the project fosters a more interconnected research ecosystem. Scientific impact includes the integration of diverse expertise, leading to more holistic research approaches, accelerated discovery, and enhanced reproducibility. Economic impact stems from more efficient resource use, avoiding duplication of effort, and enabling

multi-sectoral innovation, which can stimulate market growth and collaborative business models. Societal impact is delivered through research outcomes that are informed by multiple perspectives and disciplines, ensuring more comprehensive solutions to societal challenges and improved public access to research outputs.

Impact 3: Wide ecosystem of multidisciplinary datasets and tools enabling seamless discovery, access, and reuse of research outputs within EOSC: The creation of an integrated ecosystem of datasets and tools ensures that researchers can easily find, access, and reuse high-quality resources. Scientific impact includes accelerating discovery, supporting large-scale analyses, and enabling data-driven research across disciplines. Economic impact is generated through increased efficiency and productivity in research and innovation activities, as well as through the facilitation of new services and applications based on shared datasets. Societal impact is realised by broadening access to scientific knowledge, enhancing transparency, and supporting evidence-based policy-making and societal decision-making.

Impact 4: Progressive improvement of FAIRness in EOSC; increased quality of research; reproducibility of science greatly simplified; EOSC Data Commons services recognised as high-quality services: The project will advance the adoption of FAIR principles, improving data management practices and ensuring that research outputs are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Scientific impact includes higher-quality, reproducible research and strengthened trust in scientific findings. Economic impact arises from more efficient and reliable research workflows, which reduce costs and accelerate innovation cycles, and from the recognition of EOSC services as high-quality resources that can underpin commercial and academic applications. Societal impact is delivered through increased confidence in science, more transparent research practices, and the broader availability of reliable data and services that support societal problem-solving and innovation.

In the second half of the project, an internal training session for assessing the social, economic and scientific impact for each of the expected impacts of the project will be sought, and therefore the impact analysis will be expanded in the next WP2 deliverables.

2.6. Next Steps

In the next six months, an iteration to update all the information linked to the three innovation management activities will be performed, in order to provide the initial progress over the baseline plan collected and described in this deliverable after the first 12 months of the project. It will be delivered for the Milestone M3 - M2.3 Interim D&C&E Progress no.1 by the end of March 2026. In order to facilitate the update a first business model workshop will be organised in order to explain the foundations of the Innovation Management System described in this section for an initial to hands-on content gathering on partners expectations on results, how to leverage them and foster their adoption in the future. The recording will be made available for the partners to keep it as a reference, and the hands-on session collected content will feed the content for the subsequent deliverables.

3. Communication, Dissemination and Service Promotion

3.1 Introduction

The Communication, Dissemination, and Outreach Strategy entails the development of tailored campaigns to increase awareness of the project, its outcomes, scientific benefits, impacts, and engagement with end-users and stakeholders. The overarching goal is to foster engagement, impact, and successful exploitation through regular outreach and tailored messages to the project's stakeholders.

The Communication and Dissemination effort in the EOSC Data Commons aims to:

1. Give visibility and promote the EOSC Data Commons assets, particularly the EOSC Matchmaker and the EOSC Data Player services, to the relevant stakeholder groups;
2. Showcase the data integration and FAIRification practices of the project's use cases and their potential impact on the relevant scientific communities to the appropriate stakeholder groups;
3. Enhance visibility and awareness of the project's vision, activities, outcomes, and services among key stakeholders and across the broader research and innovation community.

3.2 Workplan

Table 4: T2.2 Workplan

Activity #	Communication, Dissemination and Service Promotion	Timeline
1	Launch branding and social media Populate website with basic project information Start monitor potential events for participation Build project's communications contacts Develop plan for communication and dissemination	April - September 2025
2	Launch external newsletter (Mailerlite, quarterly). Expand website content: service pages, Key Exploitable Results, use case profiles. Promote the project at events. Initial service teasers: introduce EOSC Matchmaker & Data Player through news items and LinkedIn posts. First dissemination campaign: "EOSC Data Commons: Building the Research Data Ecosystem" (awareness focus).	October - December 2025
3	Webinar: 1st user-facing webinar introducing EOSC Matchmaker. Community engagement: launch survey to identify researcher expectations. Plan presence at RDA (Mar 26): early results from use cases.	January - March 2026

Activity #	Communication, Dissemination and Service Promotion	Timeline
	Newsletter #2: focus on early service uptake and community feedback.	
4	TNC 2026 (Jun-26): booth or demo for EOSC Data Player. Flyer & poster versions with focus on services and cross-disciplinary relevance. User stories campaign: highlight 2–3 use case workflows (website + LinkedIn series). Newsletter #3 with practical examples of service usage. Awareness and capacity building with data stewards/librarians (at LIBER2026?) on services	April - June 2026
5	EGI Conference 2026: joint booth, service demos, dedicated session. Hands-on training: online tutorial sessions for integrating services. Service promotion push: “From Discovery to Reproducibility” campaign, cross-promoted via EOSC Association channels. Newsletter #4 featuring training resources.	July - September 2026
6	EOSC Symposium 2026: demonstration of mature services. Impact campaign: publish “One Year of EOSC Data Commons Services” highlights report. Community video testimonials: capture voices of researchers using Matchmaker & Data Player. Newsletter #5: wrap-up of 2026, preview of 2027 activities. Evaluation and strategy update: revise KPIs and outreach plan for 2027.	October - December 2026

3.2 Communications Channels and Tools

To support the dissemination and potential use of project results, this section outlines an initial set of planned activities and tools designed to keep stakeholders informed about ongoing developments. These efforts will be periodically reviewed to ensure the messages are clear, the chosen communication channels are suitable, and the intended audiences are being reached effectively.

EOSC Data Commons relies on the expertise and networks of its partners, who are well-positioned to share information about the project within their professional communities.

The following resources are available at M6:

- [Project Website](#): The EOSC Data Commons website provides not only project updates and news. It also provides access to deliverables and publications, and supports stakeholder engagement and resource sharing.
- [LinkedIn Account](#): It serves as the project’s primary social media platform for informing about the project, promoting its services, and engaging audiences.

- [Bluesky Account](#): We decided to explore the Bluesky account instead of using the traditional X. Given the platform's early stage of development and currently limited user base, we will monitor its progress to determine the relevance of maintaining a presence there.
- EOSC Data Commons Brand guide (available to project partners): Offers a collection of guidelines ensuring proper use of the EDC logo, colours, fonts, etc. to ensure the consistency of the brand across various platforms.
- Presentation and Document Templates: Provide a unified format for project presentations and documents in different formats. The templates are accessible to project partners on the project's Confluence space.
- Dissemination activity tracking and related procedures (via a Confluence page): Enables the tracking of all dissemination activities.

A database of partners' communication contacts is being developed to ensure the timely dissemination of relevant information to the proper channels.

3.3 Project Branding

The EOSC Data Commons logo adheres to the coordinated EOSC branding, as promoted by the EOSC Association starting in 2021. This approach addressed the need for a more consistent identity across the EOSC community in Horizon Europe and has been widely adopted by all EOSC-funded projects.

There is a visual addition to the logo, which is a circle around the double M in "Commons". That element can also be used as a standalone image (e.g. for stickers).

The project produced a brand manual in M0; the manual is available to the Consortium via Confluence, including information on the correct colours, fonts and logo usage, to allow all project partners to align and produce their project-related content.

The logo colours (Light Blue #009fe3, Dark blue #001f30) were chosen from the list indicated in the EOSC Association Corporate Design Manual⁹, and the two font styles (Quicksand for titles and Roboto for body) also follow the overall style implemented by the EOSC Association and a majority of EOSC-related projects.

3.3.1 Communication package and templates

Based on the established visual identity, the communication team created templates to complement the Communication Toolkit in M0.

- Presentation template - Google Slides, PPT, LaTeX
- Video conference background
- Letterhead template
- Deliverable template

3.3.2 Materials

A range of complementary gadgets and dissemination materials have already been designed and used in the first few months of the project, including pens, A5 Notepads and stickers

⁹ https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/EOSC-Corporate-Design-Manual_HR.pdf

that were distributed at the project's kick-off meeting in April 2025 and at EGI2025, which took place in Santander, Spain (see Annex 3 for more details). New material will be produced as the project progresses, including project flyers, posters and roll-ups for exhibitions and conferences. In addition to this, we will organise regular workshops with partners, especially the use case representatives, to make sure we capture their communication and dissemination needs and produce the correct materials.

3.4 Website

The EOSC Data Commons website is the central piece of the project's online presence, and it was designed in line with the general EOSC branding for better consistency.

It was launched in M1 (Apr-25) and has been expanded to include key project information such as partners, use cases, services, news and events by M3 (Jul-25). The website is hosted by the company NOIS3 in Rome, Italy.

New content is expected to be created through the second half of 2025, including pages for the services, the project's key exploitable results and additional information about the use cases.

The EOSC Data Commons website utilises [Matomo](#) analytics to enhance user experience and improve site performance. Matomo is a secure, open-source web analytics platform that respects user privacy while providing detailed insights into website traffic and user behaviour. By analysing these metrics, EOSC Data Commons can optimise content, ensure user engagement, and make data-driven decisions to better serve the needs of our visitors.

3.5 Social media

LinkedIn¹⁰ serves as the primary social media channel for EOSC Data Commons, offering a professional platform to share project updates, engage with stakeholders, and foster a growing community of followers. Through LinkedIn, we will disseminate key information, highlight achievements, and facilitate networking opportunities, ensuring our project reaches a broad and relevant audience within the research and innovation sectors.

LinkedIn is also the main channel adopted by other key initiatives in the community, such as the EOSC Association and other relevant Horizon Europe projects (e.g. OSCARS). We will focus our efforts on LinkedIn, which provides a stable and feature-rich platform for professional networking and project communication in our target communities.

The project has decided not to use X due to its downward trend in user engagement and the increasing limitation of features to paid accounts. We created a BlueSky¹¹ account to test community engagement.

¹⁰ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eosc-data-commons/>

¹¹ <https://bsky.app/profile/eosc-data-commons.bsky.social>

3.6 Newsletters

3.6.1 External Newsletter

EOSC Data Commons plans to start its newsletter in Q4 2025, when some relevant project updates will be available. A campaign will start earlier to promote the newsletter and grow the readers' base.

We chose the Mailerlite, a cloud-based platform, to manage and distribute the EOSC Data Commons project newsletter. It will be published quarterly, featuring comprehensive updates on KERs, project milestones, upcoming events, and community opportunities. Through the newsletter, we plan to inform and engage stakeholders with the latest developments and opportunities in the project.

3.6.2 Internal Newsletter

The project will deliver an internal newsletter to ensure consistent and transparent communication across all team members and stakeholders. The newsletter will provide regular updates on key milestones, upcoming deadlines, recent achievements, and any shifts in project scope or priorities. This approach will help maintain alignment, promote cross-functional awareness, and reinforce shared goals. We plan to issue the newsletter whenever needed, in accordance with the plans and deadlines of WP1 and the project office team.

3.7 Events

EOSC Data Commons will maintain a strategic and coordinated presence at relevant scientific, technical, and policy events throughout the project duration. Upcoming events will be initially identified and flagged during Activity Management Board (AMB), General Assembly (GA) meetings and WP7 meetings, with follow-up planning and decisions made by WP2 in collaboration with the Project Management Team.

To streamline event coordination, a shared table on the Confluence platform will act as a centralised calendar where all partners can flag potential dissemination opportunities and upcoming deadlines. This approach helps ensure that EOSC Data Commons takes advantage of relevant engagement opportunities across sectors and domains. Past event participation will also be logged via this channel for internal reporting and lesson-sharing.

3.7.1 Project events

EOSC Data Commons is committed to organising a range of project events to foster collaboration, share knowledge, and enhance the impact of our work. EOSC Data Commons workshops will bring together key stakeholders, including researchers and policymakers, to discuss critical topics, exchange ideas, and develop solutions that advance EOSC.

WP2 will support impactful presence at events by coordinating the development of visual and promotional materials, including flyers, roll-ups, presentation templates and branded

booth kits. These assets will support partners representing EOSC Data Commons at external events, either as standalone representatives or through joint booths with related projects and initiatives.

3.7.2 Third-party events

EOSC Data Commons is dedicated to actively participating in key third-party events to showcase the project's progress and engage with the broader scientific and research community. The project's involvement will include delivering presentations, presenting posters and demonstrations, taking on speaking roles, and hosting booths at exhibitions. This multi-faceted approach ensures that results and advancements can effectively be communicated, valuable feedback can be gathered, and new collaborations can be forged. Key events on the project calendar include the annual EOSC Symposium when the call for contributions allow for more active participation, the annual EGI Conference, and the annual TNC organised by GÉANT. Participation in COAR Annual Meetings, RDA conferences and Open Repositories might depend on the service and solutions development status. Additionally, EOSC Data Commons aims to be present at the biannual Open Science FAIR and EUDAT Conference, among other relevant events periodically identified by the consortium. These platforms provide invaluable opportunities to connect with stakeholders, share insights, and highlight the innovative solutions and resources developed by EOSC Data Commons. Active participation in these events underscores the project's commitment to fostering an inclusive and dynamic EOSC ecosystem. Also, EOSC Data Commons will leverage the consortium's networks to ensure adequate project's dissemination at institutional and national events.

3.8 Service Promotion

EOSC Data Commons will deliver two services:

1. EOSC Matchmaker: AI-Based Analytics-Oriented Metadata Warehouse and Discovery Service. It aggregates and enriches metadata from repositories in a Metadata Warehouse dataset discovery and links with analytics tools in a format that other services can use to run tasks automatically.
2. EOSC Data Player: Data Analysis Orchestration and Deployment Service. It manages and runs data analysis tools. It uses a single, consistent way to access data and can work with different types of computing systems by automatically choosing and starting the right ones when needed.

The promotion plan will focus on various aspects, starting with:

Awareness Raising

Objective: Introduce EOSC Matchmaker and EOSC Data Player to research communities across disciplines (e.g., social sciences, humanities, life sciences, environmental sciences) by leveraging partners' networks.

Message: Stress that the services will support discovery, reproducibility, and cross-disciplinary integration-critical steps toward making EOSC a go-to research ecosystem.

Engagement and Usage

Objective: Encourage hands-on use by researchers, data stewards, librarians, RDM professionals, and infrastructure providers.

Message: Direct usage reinforces value; feedback helps refine features; user stories drive peer uptake.

Capacity Building & Sustainability

Objective: Equip support staff (e.g., research software engineers, data stewards) with knowledge to integrate these services into workflows.

Message: Broad, capable support fosters adoption and ensures long-term integration into EOSC.

The messaging will highlight the following aspects:

- **FAIRNESS:** how EOSC Matchmaker enriches metadata for Findability, and how EOSC Data Player enhances Reuse and Reproducibility via standardised execution.
- **Simplified Discovery & Analytics:** EOSC Matchmaker improves metadata search; Data Player automates compute orchestration.
- **Cross-disciplinary Relevance:** Designed for researchers from the humanities to environmental sciences.
- **Time-saving & Scalability:** Streamlines workflows, enabling researchers to focus on insight rather than infrastructure.

Community engagement will utilise the project's Use Cases to capture real-world examples across disciplines, leveraging the experience of the services. These user stories will highlight workflows where EOSC Matchmaker streamlined discovery or EOSC Data Player improved reproducibility.

We will also leverage EOSC channels to inform policymakers and infrastructure partners.

3.9 Open Access

All public deliverables, dissemination content, presentations, and scientific outputs will be deposited in the EOSC Data Commons Community on Zenodo. The platform allows for persistent storage, open access, and usage tracking via analytics dashboards. DOIs will be included in all citations, and metadata will align with FAIR principles.

3.10 Success Indicators and Evaluation Methods

The effectiveness of the communication and dissemination strategy will be systematically monitored and evaluated through a combination of quantitative and qualitative indicators, ensuring that efforts are aligned with project objectives and deliver measurable impact.

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs):

- **Website Analytics:**

- Number of unique visitors and page views to the EOSC Data Commons website.
- Bounce rate and average session duration indicate engagement with content.
- Download statistics for training materials, and other resources.
- **Social Media Engagement**
 - Growth in followers on primary platforms (LinkedIn, Bluesky).
 - Number of impressions, likes, shares, and comments on posts.
 - Performance monitoring will be conducted using analytics tools for all channels.
- **Event Participation and Outreach:**
 - Number of external events where EOSC Data Commons is presented through presentations, demos, or booths.
 - Number of attendees at EOSC Data Commons-hosted events (workshops, webinars).
 - Qualitative feedback from event participants on the clarity and usefulness of EOSC Data Commons information.
- **Publications and Open Access:**
 - Number of project brochures, flyers, public deliverables, and onboarding toolkits published on the EOSC Data Commons website and Zenodo.
 - Number of scientific publications acknowledging EOSC Data Commons funding and deposited in the Zenodo community.
 - Usage tracking of materials via Zenodo analytics dashboards.
 - Number of Deliverable views on Zenodo.
- **Media and Press Coverage:**
 - Number of press releases issued coinciding with major milestones.
- **Email Communication (where applicable):**
 - Open rates and click-through rates for event invitations, training announcements, and open call alerts.

Evaluation Methods:

- **Regular Monitoring and Reporting:** WP2 will regularly update the project news section on the website and maintain a shared table on the Confluence platform to track dissemination activities and event participation.
- **Analytics Tools:** Utilise built-in analytics for the website and social media platforms to gather quantitative data on reach and engagement.
- **Feedback Mechanisms:** Collect qualitative feedback through surveys at events, during training sessions, and via direct interactions with stakeholders.
- **Content Review:** Quarterly content reviews will be conducted to optimise communication efforts and adapt the platform mix based on insights from monitoring and evaluation.
- **Coordination with Partners:** Leverage partner reports and analytics from external hosts (e.g., EGI newsletter, EOSC Forum) for broader dissemination efforts.
- **Periodic Review and Adjustment:** This strategy is dynamic and responsive, with a periodic review process ensuring adaptive improvements throughout the project lifecycle.

3.12 Next Steps

In the short term, the task priority will be to finalise the expansion of the EOSC Data Commons website and ensure full consistency with the project's branding. At the same time, we will launch the external newsletter and run a dedicated campaign to grow its readership through partner networks and targeted outreach. Initial service awareness activities will also be kicked off, using project news items, teaser content, and short LinkedIn posts to introduce the EOSC Matchmaker and EOSC Data Player to the community.

Moving into the medium term, efforts will shift towards more active service promotion. Demonstrations, use case showcases, and online events will be organised to highlight the practical benefits of the services. Hands-on engagement will be deepened through tutorials and workshops with research support staff, while user stories from project use cases will be collected and published to illustrate real-world value. During this phase, EOSC Data Commons will also reinforce its presence at key community events, ensuring that both services and project outcomes reach broad and relevant audiences.

In the long term, we will focus on consolidating service adoption and demonstrating tangible impact. Communication campaigns will highlight the added value of the EOSC Data Commons services, positioning them as integral components of the EOSC ecosystem. Uptake and user experiences will be documented through public reports, testimonials, and case studies, providing evidence of benefits across disciplines. Based on analytics and feedback collected throughout 2026, the dissemination strategy will be refined to maximise engagement, sustainability, and long-term relevance.

4. Stakeholder and User Community Engagement, Training and Feedback

4.1 Introduction

The Stakeholder and User Community Engagement strategy will coordinate the engagement of user research communities (including repository owners) represented in the major use cases for the EOSC Data Commons Project. As such, we will undertake an analysis of the main use cases, needs, and readiness levels of stakeholders to participate in the project, beginning with a survey of the major data providers (repositories and other participating platforms). Based on this feedback and some targeted focus group activities, we will develop a tailored strategy to (1) provide technical recommendations for training activities so that data providers in the project can contribute their content to the data commons, and (2) ensure that the data commons is able to respond to the major use cases and functionalities required by a variety of users and stakeholder communities. The work plan for this activity is provided below.

4.2 Work Plan

We designed the work plan for this task around six distinct but inter-connected activities:

Table 5: T2.3 Workplan

Activity #	User Engagement Set up and initial feedback collection	Timeline
1	Identify the major use cases and different user communities for the project (repositories, research communities, HPC, policy makers, industry)	July - August 2025
2	Undertake a survey of participating repositories to: 1) assess their current practices related to discoverability and interoperability and 2) learn more about the current user communities and their use cases	September - December 2025
3	Hold focus groups with other stakeholders about the value proposition of the project and potential uses for their community	September - December 2025
4	Analyse the survey results and outcomes and assess the current practices compared with user needs. Develop technical recommendations for participating EOSC Data Commons infrastructures to enable data discoverability	January - March 2026
5	Develop a plan to support repositories and other stakeholders to adopt recommendations	April - May 2026
6	Undertake a variety of community activities (included in the plan) to support the adoption of recommendations and engagement with broader stakeholder communities	June - December 2026

4.3 Identify major use cases and communities

The main goal of this task is to identify and gather information about the use cases of the EOSC Data Commons project partners. Based on data collected during initial project meetings and discussions with other project participants, we identified three major communities that will be targeted as key stakeholders in this effort:

- 1) **Repositories and other data providers:** These are project partners that will be contributing their content to the EOSC Data Commons. There are a total of 15 repositories and other platforms that are participating in the project. The aim will be to understand how they currently expose content to external services, identify recommended practices for contributing content to the data commons, and develop technical recommendations that repositories and platforms can adopt to contribute to the project;
- 2) **Research communities:** These are the research communities that will be the potential users of the EOSC Data Commons. We will gain initial insights into different domain research communities through a survey of participating repositories and platforms. This will be supplemented by specific focus groups with domain communities to understand their research needs related to the EOSC Data Commons project;
- 3) **Other communities (industry & public authorities):** These include representatives from the public and private sectors such as governmental bodies and local

authorities as well as businesses expected to benefit from project results. We aim to Public authorities and businesses to increase the knowledge about EOSC for data-driven policymaking and to foster future opportunities for EOSC Data Commons Services out of traditional scientific communities.

4.3 Survey

Once we have identified participating repositories and their affiliated research communities, we are now focusing on learning more about their technical capacity and readiness to participate in the EOSC Data Commons project, along with gaining a better understanding of the use cases of their affiliated research communities. To accomplish this, we designed a survey of repositories / platforms, which was disseminated in mid-September (survey questions are available in Annex 4). The purpose of this survey is to understand the current practices of content providers (repository and platforms) to understand how they are currently exposing content to users, other systems, and machines - and identify any barriers to their participation in the EOSC Data Commons Project." The survey was sent on September 15th; participants have until October 13th, 2025, to submit their responses.

4.4 Next Steps

In the next six months, we will focus on analysing survey responses to identify technical issues that need to be addressed by data providers. At the same time we will conduct focus group sessions with other stakeholders, including public authorities and industry, to gain their insights into the value proposition of the project and the potential beneficial uses for their community. We hope to gain clear data points that enable us to assess the current practices compared with user needs. These insights will inform our efforts to develop technical recommendations, guidelines, and best practices for repositories to effectively participate in the EOSC Data Commons infrastructures to enable data discoverability.

5. Conclusions and next steps

This document has presented the Communications, Dissemination, Exploitation and Engagement Plan for the project. It includes the description of the workplan, the initially developed tools and templates and the strategy and steps that will be applied to ensure that project results are effectively captured, protected, disseminated, and exploited for maximum impact.

Some important milestones have happened during the first months within the set-up phase of the project, for relevant communications activities.

- March 2025. M1 - M2.1 Communication package available
- April 2025. M2 - M2.2 Website launched
- September 2025 - D2.1 Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Engagement Plan

Figure 4: Project Schedule

Next major check-point is in March 2026 - with the delivery of the M3 - M2.3 Interim D&C&E Progress no.1, where the progress against the baseline plan will be drafted. This progress will be updated by M18 (September 2026) in D2.2 Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Engagement Progress Report that will focus on the initial results gathering and related information on Ownership, IPR, Access information and exploitation expectations for all the partners, dissemination and communications linked to introducing the project and its progress and providing the early feedback from the community engagement activities. Also the initial policy brief (D2.3) deliverable is expected September 2026. A second milestone to update on the progress is expected by March 2026 (M4 - M2.4 Interim D&C&E Progress no.2) and final major milestone will happen by the end of the project with the organisation of the Final Event (M5 - M2.5 Final Event) and the final deliverable D2.4 Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Engagement Final Report that will focus on the adoption and future uptake of the project results, the promotion of the success stories of the project and the delivery of the training plan for the user communities.

Acronyms

Table 6: Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
AI-MWDS	AI-based Analytics Oriented Metadata Warehouse and Discovery Service (EOSC Matchmaker)
DAODS	EOSC Data Commons Execution Service (EOSC Data Player)
DoA	Description of Action
EDC	EOSC Data Commons
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
HRP	Horizon Results Platform
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
OLA	Operation Level Agreement
RI	Research Infrastructures
RDM	Research Data Management
ROL	Results Ownership List
SLA	Service Level Agreement
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

Annex 1. EOSC Related Projects

Table 7: EOSC projects for collaboration

Acronym	Short summary	Reason for interest	Collaboration type	Potential collaboration
AI4EOSC	Artificial Intelligence for the European Open Science Cloud	Potential deployment platform (marketplace) for the project outputs Potential platform for running user workloads (analytics) / services	Technology Source / Exploitation Purpose (as technology/service adoption)	Adoption of Infrastructure Manager + TOSCA templates Potential deployment platform (marketplace) for the project outputs Potential platform for running user workloads (analytics) / services
AqualNFRA	InfrA Federated European FAIR and open Research Ecosystem for oceans, seas, coastal and inland watersastructure for Marine and Inland Water Research	Potential data source / users in the marine sciences domains	Requirements Source / Feedback Purpose. Exploitation Purpose (as users)	Interaction at events
Blue-Cloud 2026	A Federated European FAIR and open Research Ecosystem for oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters	Potential data source / users in the marine sciences domains Already in close collaboration with EGI - using EGI services for data analytics	Requirements Source / Feedback Purpose. Exploitation Purpose (as users)	Interaction at events (e.g. EGI conference)
CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC	Fair Data and Innovative Services for Magnifying the Climate Adaptation	Development of services focused on climate related research, these could be	Requirements Source, Exploitation Purpose	Development of services focused on climate related research, these could be

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Acronym	Short summary	Reason for interest	Collaboration type	Potential collaboration
	potential of European Communities	potentially source for tools/data in WP4		potentially source for tools/data in WP4
CRAFT-OA	Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access	EGI is involved in AAI provision Interesting for WP4 - Metadata Harvesting & FAIR	Potential Requirements Source and Technology Source	Assessment of deliverables, project documentation and technologies/services
DataGEMS	Data Discovery Platform with Generalized Exploratory, Management, and Search Capabilities	Same call Similar services being implemented (e.g. NL Dataset Discovery and AI Assisted Exploration)	Feedback Purpose, Dissemination Purpose	Potential Cross-Project Joint dissemination activity
EOSC Beyond	Advancing innovation and collaboration for research	EGI is involved Core Innovation Sandbox can used as test & validation platform for EDC services	Exploitation Purpose (as technology and service validation)	Use of core innovation sandbox for validation of EDC services
EOSC EDEN	Enhancing Digital preservation strategies at European and National level	DANS is EDEN Partners Developing a specification for Metadata that should be considered by EDC under WP4-WP5	Requirements Source / Feedback purpose	Alignment with Metadata specification
EOSC GRAVITY	Supporting the EOSC Partnership in further consolidating the coordination and sustainability of the EOSC ecosystem	EGI is partner Switch is partner Developing the next iteration of EOSC SRIA. Supporting EOSC task forces Coordination of Horizon Europe Technology Group	Requirements Source, Feedback Purpose, Dissemination Purpose	Provision of project feedback to next iteration of EOSC SRIA Involvement in the HE Technology Group Involvement in Technical, Semantic and Interoperability Task Force,

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Acronym	Short summary	Reason for interest	Collaboration type	Potential collaboration
				FAIR metrics and digital objects Task Force (Maybe Long term preservation Task Force - for the EDC user communities)
EOSC Lumen	Linked User-driven Multidisciplinary Exploration Network	Same call Developing 4 discovery platforms	Feedback Purpose, Dissemination Purpose	Potential Cross-Project Joint dissemination activity Collaboration with the innovation platform and podcast - from an exploitation & dissemination point of view.
EOSC United	Coordination and Support Action for the Future engagement model for the EOSC Federation	EGL is partner	Feedback Purpose, Exploitation Purpose, Dissemination Purpose	Provision of project feedback to interoperability framework. Engagement in use cases and adoptions calls.
EOSC-ENTRUST	A European Network of TRUSTed research environments	Potential deployment platform for analytics from EDC	Feedback Purpose. Exploitation Purpose (as users)	Potential platform for running user workloads (analytics) / services
EOSC4Cancer				
EuroScienceGateway	Leveraging the European compute infrastructures for data-intensive research guided by FAIR principles	EGL is involved Galaxy is developed in EuroScienceGateway	Technology Source	Galaxy is one of the platforms included in the EDC Data Player
EVERSE	European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence	Potential use of the RSOKit as guidelines for software quality	Technology Source	Potential use of the RSOKit as guidelines for software quality

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Acronym	Short summary	Reason for interest	Collaboration type	Potential collaboration
FAIR-EASE	FAIR EArth Sciences & Environment services	Develop two services: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FAIR-EASE Interdisciplinary Data Discovery and Access Service, and • FAIR-EASE Earth Analytical Lab and Data Lake Possible integration of those into EDC Tools for FAIR Assessment Galaxy used also in FAIR-EASE	Technology Source (FAIR Assessment), Requirements Source (for integration of their tools), Exploitation purpose	Integration of FAIR-EASE services and tools for FAIR Assessment
FAIR2Adapt	FAIR to Adapt to Climate Change	Source for tools for the Matchmaker (e.g. ROHub) and Fair Assessment (FAIROS)	Requirements Source (for integration with ROHub), Exploitation purposes (as user)	Potential integration of ROHub as source for tools for the Matchmaker. Re-use of Fair Assessment tools
FIDELIS	Establishing A European Network of Trustworthy Digital Repositories	DANS is involved Close collaboration with EDEN for long-term preservation of data. Develop of definition of trustworthy repositories, could be relevant as a requirement source for WP4	Requirements Source, Feedback purpose, Dissemination Purpose	Alignment with any specifications from the project
GraspOS	Next Generation Research Assessment to Promote Open Science	EGI and CESNET are involved Potential use of their Enrichment tools as part of the Matchmaker	Exploitation Purpose (as users)	Potential use of their Enrichment tools as part of the Matchmaker

D2.1 Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Engagement Plan

Acronym	Short summary	Reason for interest	Collaboration type	Potential collaboration
OSCARS	Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society		Requirements Source	
OSTrails	Open Science Plan-Track-Assess Pathways	DANS is partner Expected ReUse of FAIR Toolset	Technology Source	Expected Re-use of FAIR Toolset
RAISE	Research Analysis Identifier System	Potential execution platform for user workloads	Feedback purpose, Exploitation Source	Potential execution platform for user workloads
RAISE Suite	FAIR data from collection to exploitation	Same call Follow up of RAISE (see above), potential execution platform for user workloads	Feedback purpose, Exploitation Source	Potential execution platform for user workloads
RDA TIGER	Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions	DANS is member of the consortium Support for RDA groups relevant to EOSC	Feedback Purpose, Dissemination Purpose	Provision of project feedback to the relevant RDA groups
SciLake	Scientific Data-Lake-as-a-Service	Potential reuse of technology/approaches for the Metadata Warehouse	Feedback Purpose. Technology Source	Potential reuse of technology/approaches for the Metadata Warehouse
SIESTA	Secure Interactive Environments for SensiTive data Analytics	Potential deployment platform for analytics from EDC Potential usage of tools for secure anonymisation or pseudonymisation of datasets	Feedback Purpose. Exploitation Purpose (as users)	Potential deployment platform for analytics from EDC Potential usage of tools for secure anonymisation or pseudonymisation of datasets
Skills4EOSC	Skills for the European Open Science Commons:	CMCC, CNRS and INFN are part of the consortium	Dissemination purpose	

D2.1 Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Engagement Plan

Acronym	Short summary	Reason for interest	Collaboration type	Potential collaboration
	Creating a Training Ecosystem for Open and FAIR Science	Potential promotion of EDC as base for training material		
STR-ESFRI project	Support to Reinforce the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures	Support activities in the areas of the ESFRI Roadmap process and the Landscape Analysis, the RI monitoring and the MoS platform, and in the area of EOSC, liaising with the EOSC Association with emphasis on researcher engagement and RI federation in EOSC.	Dissemination purpose	Provision of project feedback to next iteration of ESFRI Roadmap and Landscape Analysis
TITAN	Trusted environments for confidential computing and secure data sharing	Potential deployment platform for analytics from EDC		

Annex 2. Initial template for exploitable assets

Table 8: Template for Exploitable Assets

Background & Third parties Components needed	
Access for Implementation	For each background component under which conditions can it be used in the project?
Access for Exploitation	For each background component under which conditions can be used for external adoption?
Results	
Short Description	What does the asset do?
Work Done in the Project	Which were the improvements done in the project?
Documentation	Support material ?
Links	Where to find more information?
Next steps & Future Development	What are the future needs?
IP Management & Results Ownership List)	
Ownership	Who owns?
IPR	Such as Copyright, Patent, Trade Secret, etc
Access Conditions	Access License (e.g. CC, Open Source license, etc)
Innovation	
Target Groups / Users	Who will use it?
Alternatives / Substitutives	What else can be used instead?
Value Proposition	What is better in our solution?
Exploitation	
Further Research	Follow up projects, education, etc
Services	Service onboarding, Market places, Users, etc
Products	Technology Transfer, Licensing, Adoption, etc
Standardisation	Standards influenced, adopted, interoperability, etc
Sustainability	
Cost-Benefit Analysis	Costs (CAPEX, OPEX) / Expected Returns
Business Model / Business Plan	Such as SaaS, PaaS, IaaS, Maintenance and Support

Annex 3. EOSC Data Commons communications assets

Figure 5 EOSC Data Commons logo

Figure 6 EOSC Data Commons profile picture for social media channels

Figure 7 Sticker variants for distribution to partners and at events

Figure 8 Online meeting background variant

Figure 9 Moo card with QR code to the project website

Annex 4. Community Engagement Survey

Survey questions:

1. Please provide the name the repository you are representing as part of the EOSC Data Commons project (Please make sure it is listed in project internal confluence and all information is accurate)
2. Please provide your email address
3. What are the top three most prominent artifacts that your repository hold e.g., manuscripts, datasets, software source code?
 - a. Datasets
 - b. Images
 - c. manuscripts/text
 - d. Software
 - e. Code
 - f. Other
4. What top three most prominent data formats does your repository support?
 - a. CSV
 - b. TXT
 - c. PDF
 - d. XLS
 - e. Others - please list them
5. What top three most prominent metadata formats does your repository support?
 - a. Dublin Core
 - b. MODS
 - c. [Schema.org](https://schema.org/)
 - d. DataCite
 - e. DCAT
 - f. System generated metadata
 - g. None
 - h. I don't know
 - i. Others - please list them
6. Does your repository maintain links between related artifacts, for example between data and code?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
7. Who are the typical users of your repository e.g., domain-specific researchers, international scholars?

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8. Please explain briefly what your main user group uses your platform to accomplish (data process, sharing results with others)
9. Which of the following internal discovery mechanisms does your repository support:
 - a. keyword search
 - b. faceted search
 - c. Browsing
 - d. None
 - e. Please briefly describe.
10. Which of the following interoperability affordances does your repository support:
 - a. OAI-PMH
 - b. REST APIs
 - c. ResourceSync
 - d. Signposting
 - e. Others - please list them
11. If there are technical developments to your platform required to contribute your content to the EOSC Data Commons (e.g., implementing a new API), are you willing to and able to implement them?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
12. What benefit or value, specifically for your repository, do you anticipate from contributing content to the EOSC Data Commons project?
13. What would you consider to be a successful outcome for your repository based on your participation in this project?